

GLOBAL PEDAGOGIC IN PRIMARY EDUCATION TEACHER'S IMAGE IN PROBLEM SOLVING

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Abstract.

In this article, global pedagogical problems in primary education and their causes, opinions about the importance of the image of the teacher in their elimination are highlighted.

Keywords: primary education, global, problem, physiology, attention, modern teaching tools, game activity, study activity.

Introduction:

It is known that today attention is being paid to quality science. Bringing up independent, creative, enterprising young people who care about the future of the country is rising to the level of state policy. Primary education plays an extremely important role in fulfilling such a responsible task. Attention to primary education is attention to the whole nation and all people. Nowadays, the use of modern techniques and technologies and the correct formation of their worldview are very important in providing primary education to the young generation. Many laws and regulations are being adopted in our country in order to make primary education of high quality and meet the requirements of the times.

The main part. The rapid development of science and technology is the reason for achieving great achievements. At the same time, there are global pedagogical problems that need to be solved. First, let's talk about the global concept. Global-Latin globe-globe earth-planet, it is understood as a set of national economies connected to each other through the system of international division of labor, economic and political relations, one of the unique features of the process of changing the composition of the world economy. In 1985, the well-known American scientist R. Robertson introduced the term "globalization" into a scientific context and interpreted this concept as a process that reflects the narrowing of our planet in the minds of people and the understanding of the world as a whole, as well as the unification of the world and the strengthening of interactions between people. Therefore, a global problem is a problem that is equally important for all people on earth.

Problem-Greek prosoba-task, task in the broad sense of a complex theoretical or practical problem that requires learning, solving; a contradictory situation that acts in the form of contradictory situations in the explanation of any phenomena, objects, processes in science and requires an adequate theory to solve it; problems in life are formulated in a way that people can understand. An important condition for successfully solving the problem is to formulate it correctly.

Primary school is the most important period in a child's life. Primary education is the stage of general secondary education.

In Uzbekistan, primary education is the first period of teaching children in grades 1-4 and their spiritual development. At the age of 7-10, various physical and mental changes begin to

occur in students. Various psychological conditions are also observed. A student who has just started attending school begins to lose his kindergarten, his toys, and the fun games he plays with his friends in kindergarten. Goes from game activity to study activity. Game activity is the first activity of children, it is a way of processing the impressions of the surrounding world. Reading activity is the period after the game activity, and it is considered the period of learning and learning of a person. In this period, taking into account the mental state of children, it is the main task of a primary school teacher to be able to instill respect for science and school, to properly organize lessons.

Pedagogical scientist A.K.Morkova in her research considers the methodical training of a primary school teacher as a mental state that allows independent and responsible work, consisting of the results of human labor, the ability and skills of a person to perform certain labor tasks admits.¹

B.S.Abdullayeva made the following comments in her scientific works. The professional potential and level of education of the primary school teacher, child psychology, are important in improving the quality of primary education nowadays. It is desirable to form the necessary skills in primary school students, to bring the quality and efficiency of primary education to a new level, and to introduce modern teaching tools into practice. Modern teaching aids are a set of equipment that provides visualization in the delivery of information by the teacher to the learner.²

To concentrate and maintain the attention of students of this age requires great skill from the pedagogue. Attention is the attraction of the subject's activity to an object or event. It is a necessary condition for the effectiveness of any conscious activity. A number of psychologists have worked to study the problem of attention in primary school students.

Among them are A.R. Luria, S.L. Rubenstein, A.N. Leontev, L.S. Vygotsky and others. They gave different psychological definitions of attention. According to K.D.Ushensky, "Attention is the only door of our spiritual life that everything that enters our mind passes through this door."³

S. Rubenstein noted that "Attention does not depend on the mind or the properties of the object, its important aspect is to direct attention to the object."⁴

Based on the conducted investigations, N. Strakhov came to the conclusion that attention is a multi-functional process. P. Bolonsky noted that "after the mind of elementary school students is focused on one object, he does not see the things and events around him".⁵

Therefore, when choosing an object for elementary school students, it is also worth noting that the object is interesting. Taking into account these aspects, the teacher should conduct the lesson on the basis of various bright colors, colorful methods, and interesting games that attract the attention of children and keep their attention for a long time. Conducting various exercises, quick sayings, competitions, and repetition exercises to improve the student's mental ability, improve memory, and encourage thinking has a good effect.

¹ Abduraxmonova N.N 'Bo 'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini metodik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish muammosining pedagogik zaruriyati maqolasi

² Abduraxmonova N.N 'Bo 'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchisining metodik tayyorgarkigin itakomillashtirish muammosining pedagogik zaruriyati' maqolasi

³ Ushenskiy 'Insoniy ishlarni tuzatishhaqida umumiy maslahatlar'' asari.

⁴ S.Rubenshteyn 'Umumiy psixologiya asoslari' asari.

⁵ <http://kompu.info>

Rapid changes occur not only in the cognitive process of elementary school students, but also in their physiological sphere. If we explain the concept of physiology here, Physiology is the Greek word for nature and logic, a science that studies organisms and their parts, systems, organs, tissues, and life activities. If during the lesson, the pedagogue does not control the students' sitting in one place for a long time, standing for a long time, heavy physical activity, various defects will appear in the development of the students. So, in addition to the pedagogue's skill in teaching, his observability is lacking in preventing problems that may arise in physiological development.

The wrong sitting of the student at the desk also causes various problems. When the student is sitting at the desk, he should keep his height straight, his legs and knees should touch the ground forming an angle of 90 degrees, and the child's spine should be touching the back of the chair. The distance between the student's chair and the edge of the desk should be in the specified order so as not to squeeze the child. If the elementary school teacher does not pay attention to these situations, global problems such as improper development of the next generation may arise. In order to prevent such situations as fatigue, boredom, yawning, i.e. rapid brain fatigue in students of this age, the pedagogue should open the window every 10-15 minutes and ventilate the room even during breaks.

In the period of primary education, in addition to primary education, students are also taught basic social and moral concepts. It is a very important period in the formation of a child as a person, and he begins to understand the essence of the concepts of society and personality. Our Eastern scholars and great thinkers have emphasized that primary education is very important. Among them, Abu Rayhan Beruni said about primary education, "Our goal is not to tire the student. Reading something over and over again is boring and tiring. If the student moves from one issue to another, it is as if he is walking in different gardens, as soon as he passes one garden, another garden begins. One wants to see and watch them all. Every new thing brings pleasure."⁶

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⁶B.M.Muhammadovich, Ch.V.Petrovna ,B.V. Muhiddinovna "Sharq mutafakkirlari ta'lim va o'qitish masalalari haqida" maqola

passes one garden, another garden begins. One wants to see and watch them all. Every new thing brings pleasure" wrote that.⁷

We know that elementary school students and even their parents are very interested in sitting at the first desk. The number of students in the class is twenty-five-thirty, and the number of first desks is only two or three. So, what should a pedagogue do in such a situation? Examining the medical record of all students in the class, that is, moving children with certain visual impairments to the front row, then taking into account height, and also possible short students it is necessary to move to the previous lines. In such a situation, the teacher should act very rationally and explain to all students and their parents. During the lesson, if more group methods are used, children's respect for each other will increase, and the importance of the first desk will disappear.

One of the problems of this period is that the teacher cannot complete the assigned lesson completely, as a result of not being able to allocate time properly, and gives the child all the remaining examples, problems, and exercises as homework. As a result of this, negative aspects such as boredom and difficulty in completing lessons arise in the student who is just starting to study. In order to prevent such negative aspects, the teacher should organize the lesson correctly, divide the time and complete the lessons according to the established standard, and give homework according to the age of the student. It is definitely in the hands of the pedagogue to be able to instill a good love for this science in the student.

Summary. So, we can say that primary education is very global, because if the foundation of the house is the foundation, if the house is strong, if it is beautiful, then the person will grow up as a person, and the primary education will be brought up as a perfect person is extremely incomparable. Therefore, primary education is always global. First of all, the role of the pedagogue and of course the parents is important in solving the above-mentioned problems in primary education in a timely and reasonable manner.

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⁷ B.M.Muhammadovich, Ch.V.Petrovna, B.V.Muhiddinova Sharq mutafakkirlari ta'lim, tarbiya va o'qitish masalalari haqida" maqola

